

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Formulation And Preliminary Evaluation of Chia Seeds (*Salvia Hispanica*) Powder as A Functional Health Supplement

Lande Sanika, Vighe Shital, Wable Aniket*, Sinare Omkar, Datir Vinay, Jadhav Gayatri, Gaikwad Vijay

Dr. Kolpe Institute of Pharmacy, Kolpewadi.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 03 June 2026

Keywords:

Chia seeds, functional food, herbal churna, weight management, digestion, nutritional supplement

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20525768

ABSTRACT

The present study aims to develop a multi-functional chia seed churn intended to support weight management, improve digestion and promote overall health. Chia seed are rich in essential such as dietary fibers, omega 3 fatty acids, proteins and antioxidants which contribute to their health promoting properties. In this formulation chia seeds were blended with other natural ingredients including chia seeds, flax seeds, oats, fennel, almonds, black salt, jeera and dry ginger powder to enhance both nutritional value and functional benefits. The preparation method involves steps such as cleaning, shade drying, light roasting, mixing to produce a fine powder. The formulated churn is expected to aid digestion, weight management and contribute a better skin and hair health. It also demonstrated acceptable texture and stability when stored under proper airtight container. Therefore, the developed chia seeds churn may serve as a natural and beneficial dietary supplement for supporting a healthy lifestyle.

INTRODUCTION

Chia seeds (*salvia hispanica*) consider as a functional food because of their rich nutritional properties. They contain high level of dietary fiber, protein, omega-3 fatty acids, along with essential vitamins and minerals that supports overall health. Regular intake of chia seeds has been linked with better digestion, effective weight management or weight control and improved metabolic function.

In current situation there has been an increasing preference for natural and plant-based supplements. As people are becoming more conscious about maintaining a healthy lifestyle and balanced nutrition or a balanced diet.

Powder formulation are widely preferred due to their ease of consumption and versatility, as they can be mixed with liquids such as water or milk. These forms may also enhance the absorption or nutrients in the body.

***Corresponding Author:** Wable Aniket

Address: *Dr. Kolpe Institute of Pharmacy, Kolpewadi..*

Email ✉: wableaniket08@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Churn, which is a traditional powdered preparation, is commonly used because of its simplicity, longer shelf life and effectiveness. The combination of chia seeds with other natural ingredients can improve both nutritional quality and functional benefit.

Such formulation may also help in supporting digestion, increasing energy, weight management and promoting healthy skin and hair.

Hence, the present study is focused on the preparation and evaluation of chia seed powder as a health supplement. The objective is to create a natural, nutrient-rich and easy to use formulation that may assist in weight management, digestive health and overall well-being.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF CHIA SEED POWDER:

SR.NO	AUTHOR/ YEAR	STUDY FOCUS	KEY FINDINGS	CONCLUSION
1	Knez hrncic et al 2019	Nutritional profile of chia seeds	Rich in fiber, omega-3, protein, antioxidants	Use full as a functional food
2	MDPI,2020	Polyphenols in chia seeds	High antioxidants activity reduce oxidative stress	Supports overall Health
3	Research gate studies,2022	Digestion and satiety	Forms gel-like structure, improve digestion	Helps in weight management
4	Harvard health, 2023	Health benefits	Supports heart health and metabolism	Good dietary supplement
5	WebMD, 2022	General use	Improve digestion and provide nutrients	Safe for regular consumption
6	Polyherbal studies	Churn formulation	Combination increases effectiveness	Better therapeutic value
7	Flaxseed research	Omega -3 and lignans	Improve skin and hair health	Enhance nutritional value

1. CHIA SEEDS

Chia seeds are widely used in churn formulation because of their rich nutritional composition and functional properties.

They are an excellent source of dietary fiber, omega 3 fatty acids, protein and antioxidant which

contribute to various health benefits. Their ability to absorb water and promote satiety makes them useful in formulation intended for digestion support and weight management.

FIG :1 CHIA SEEDS AND CHIA SEEDS POWDER

TOXONOMY OF CHIA SSEDS:

CLASSIFICATION RANK	TOXONOMY
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Lamiales
Family	Lamiaceae
Genus	Salvia
Species	Salvia hispanica

Flax seeds are commonly incorporated into churn formulation because of their rich nutritional composition and functional benefits.

They are an excellent source of dietary fiber, omega-3 fatty acids, lignans and antioxidants which contribute to improved digestion, enhanced satiety and overall well- being.

Their inclusion in the formulation and support heart health, weight management, skin and hair nourishment.

2: FLAX SEEDS

FIG :2 FLAX SEEDS AND FLAX SEED POWDER

TOXONOMY FLAX SEEDS

CLASSIFICATION RANK	TOXONOMY
Kingdom	Plantae
division	Magnoliopsida
class	Malpighiales
Order	Malpighiales
Family	Linaceae
Genus	Linum
species	Linum usitatissimum

Oats are widely used in churn formulation due to their content and nutritional value. They are rich in beta-glucan fiber which may help improve digestion, increase satiety and support weight management.

Oats also provide energy and contribute to the smooth texture and consistency of the formulation, making them a suitable ingredients in functional health supplements.

3: OATS (rolled oats)

FIG :3 OATS AND OATS POWDER

TOXONOMY OF OATS

CLASSIFICATION RANK	TOXONOMY
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Liliopsida
Order	Poales
Family	Poaceae
Genus	Avena
Species	Avena sativa

FIG: 4 CUMIN SEEDS AND CUMIN SEEDS POWDER

4: CUMIN SEEDS (JEERA)

Cumin seeds are digestive widely incorporated into churn formulation due to their beneficial digestive properties and characteristic aroma.

They may help improve digestion, reduce bloating and support metabolism.

In addition, cumin seeds contain antioxidants and essential nutrients that contribute to the overall functional value of formulation.

TOXONOMY OF CUMIN SEEDS

CLASSIFICATION RANK	TOXONOMY
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Apiales
Family	Apiaceae
Genus	Cuminum
species	Cuminum cyminum

4: FENNEL SEEDS (SAUNF)

Fennel seed are widely used in churn formulation because of their digestive and aromatic properties.

They may help in reducing bloating, improve digestion and support metabolism. In addition, the presence of antioxidants and essential oils enhances the functional value and palatability of the formulation.

FIG 5: FENNEL SEEDS AND FENNEL SEEDS POWDER

TOXONOMY OF FENNEL SEEDS

CLASSIFICATION RANK	TOXONOMY
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Apiales
Family	Apiaceae
Genus	Foeniculum
Species	Foeniculum vulgare

6: ALMONDS

Almonds are commonly used in churn formulation due to their rich nutritional composition and health benefits.

They are an excellent source of healthy fats, protein, vitamin E and antioxidants which contribute to overall nourishment and well-being. Their inclusion in the formulation may support energy level, skin and hair health and improve the nutritional value of the product.

FIG: 6 ALMONDS

TOXONOMY OF ALMONDS

CLASSIFICATION RANK	TOXONOMY
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Rosales
Family	Rosaceae
Genus	Prunus
Species	Prunus dulcis

7: DRY GINGER POWDER

Dry ginger powder used in churn formulations due to its digestive and therapeutic properties . it may help improve digestion, reduce bloating and support metabolism.

In addition, the presence of antioxidants and bioactive compounds contributes to the functional value of the formulation while enhancing its flavor and aroma.

FIG :7 DRY GINGER AND DRY GINGER POWDER

TOXONOMY OF DRY GINGER POWDER

CLASSIFICATION RANK	TOXONOMY
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Liliopsida
Order	Zingiberales
Family	Zingiberaceae
Genus	Zingiber
Species	Zingiber officinale

8: BLACK SALT

Black salt is widely used into churn formulations because of its digestive and flavor enhancing properties.

It may help reduce bloating, improve digestion and increase palatability of the formulation.

In addition, its traditional use in digestive preparation makes it a suitable ingredient in functional health supplements.

FIG: 8 BLACK SALT

METHODS OF PREPARATION:

- The selected ingredients were first cleaned thoroughly to remove any dust and impurities.
- They were then shade dried for about 2-3 hours to eliminate moisture content.
- After drying, each ingredient's was roasted separately at low temperature for a few minutes to improve flavor and enhance shelf life.
- The roasted materials were allowed to cool at room temperature.
- Once cool the ingredients were ground into fine powder using a mixer grinder.
- The powdered mixture was then sieved to obtain a uniform texture and to remove any coarse particles. All the powdered ingredients were mixed properly to ensure homogeneity.
- Finally dry ginger powder and black salt were added and mixed thoroughly.
- The prepared chia seed powder was stored in a clean, dry and airtight container to maintain its quality and prevent moisture absorption.

FIG :9 ALL DRIED INGREDIENTS USED IN CHURN

FORMULATION TABLE:

INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY
Chia seed	40 gm
Flax seed	20 m
Oats	15 m

Cumin seeds	10 m
Fennel seeds	10 m
Almond	5 m
Dry ginger powder	3 m
Black salt	2 m

FIG: 10 POWDER OF ALL INGREDIENTS USED IN CHURN

BATCH PREPARATION:

The formulation of chia seed powder was carried out in two batches to ensure consistency and reproducibility of the result.

Each batch was prepared using the same method and quantity of ingredients. The prepared batches were evaluated for physical and sensory properties and no significant variation was observed between batches.

OBSERVATIONAL STUDY:

BATCH NO	OBSERVATION	RESULT
Batch 1	Good texture and aroma	Acceptable
Batch 2	Similar properties	Consistent

ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION AND DOSAGE:

➤ ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION: Oral

- FREQUENCY OF ADMINISTRATION: once or twice a day
- METHOD OF CONSUMPTION: Mixed with water or milk also can be added to smoothies or other food atoms.

Storage stability	No major change stable	Stable
Moisture effect	Low moisture	Good shelf life
Color / texture change	No significant change	Acceptable

DOSAGE ACCORDING TO AGE:

CHILDREN	½ to 1 teaspoon daily
ADULT	1-2 teaspoon daily
ELDERLY	1 teaspoon daily

EVALUATION PARAMETERS:

PHYSICAL PARAMETERS:

PHYSICAL PARAMETER	OBSERVATION	RESULT
Color	Light brown	Acceptable
Texture	Fine and uniform	Good quality
Appearance	Smooth powder	Uniform
Particle size	Fine	Suitable for consumption

SENSORY PARAMETERS:

SENSORY PARAMETERS	OBSERVATION	RESULT
Taste	Slightly nutty	Palatable
Aroma	Mild and pleasant	Acceptable
Mouthfeel	Smooth	Comfortable to consume
Overall acceptability	Good	Suitable as supplement

STABILITY PARAMETER:

STABILITY PARAMETER	OBSERVATION	RESULT

ADVANTAGES OF CHIA SEED CHURNA:

- 1 Improve digestion
- 2 Helps in weight management
- 3 Provide essential nutrients
- 4 Supports skin and hair health
- 5 Boosts energy level
- 6 Easy to consume
- 7 Natural and safe formulation
- 8 Cost-effective and easy to prepare

PRECAUTION:

- Chia seed powder should always be consumed with adequate water and should be taken in dry form.
- The recommended dosage should be followed to avoid over consumption.
- It is advisable to start with small quantity especially for first-time users.
- Adequate water intake should be followed to avoid over consumption.
- Pregnant women or individuals with medical conditions should consult a doctor before use.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

PHYSICAL AND SENSORY EVALUATION OF CHIA SEED CHURNA

SR.NO	PARAMETER	OBSERVATION	EVALUATION CRITERIA	REMARK
1	Color	Light brown	Visual	Acceptable
2	Texture	Fine and uniform	By touch	Good quality
3	Aroma	Mild and pleasant	Sensory evaluation	Acceptable
4	Taste	Slightly nutty	Organoleptic test	Palatable
5	Appearance	Smooth powder	Visual	Uniform

6	Particle size	Fine	Sieving method	Suitable for use
7	Moisture content	Low	Physical observation	Good shelf life
8	Storage stability	No change observed	After storage study	Stable

FUNCTIONAL BENEFITS EVALUATION:

SR.NO	PARAMETER	OBSERVATION	INFERENCE
1	Satiety level	Increased	Helps in weight management
2	Digestion	Improved	Reduce bloating
3	Energy level	Moderate improvement	Provide sustained energy
4	Skin health	Improve texture	Due to antioxidant
5	Hair quality	Slight improvement	Nutrient support

The result presented in the tables indicate that the developed chia seed powder demonstrated satisfactory physical and sensory characteristics along with possible functional advantages.

The formulation exhibited good stability, acceptable taste and significant nutritional value indicating its suitability as a health supplements.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully focused on the formulation and preliminary evaluation of chia seeds powder as a functional health supplement.

The developed formulation exhibited acceptable physical and sensory properties, including good texture, aroma and palatability.

The use of natural ingredients contributed overall nutritional quality of the product. the formulation is rich in dietary fiber, omega-3 fatty acids and antioxidants which may help in supporting digestion, promoting satiety and assisting in weight management.

Additionally the presence of this nutrients may contribute to improve skin and hair health.

The product also demonstrated good stability under appropriate storage conditions.

Overall, the study suggests that chia seeds powder can be considered a promising natural health supplement.

However, further detailed clinical and analytical studies are required to confirm its long-term effectiveness and health benefits.

REFERENCES

1. Coates W. The Complete Guide to Chia Seeds. New York: Sterling Publishing; 2012.
2. Ullah R, Nadeem M, Khalique A, Imran M, Mehmood S, Javid A, et al. Nutritional and therapeutic perspectives of chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.): a review. J Food Sci Technol. 2016;53(4):1750-8.
3. Ixtaina VY, Nolasco SM, Tomás MC. Physical properties of chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.) seeds. Ind Crops Prod. 2008;28(3):286-93.

4. Ayerza R, Coates W. Chia: rediscovering a forgotten crop of the Aztecs. Tucson: University of Arizona Press; 2005.
5. Kokate CK. Pharmacognosy. 54th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2014.
6. Shah B, Seth AK. Textbook of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry. 2nd ed. New Delhi: Elsevier; 2010
7. Srilakshmi B. Food Science. 7th ed. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers; 2018.
8. Joshi SA. Nutrition and Dietetics. 4th ed. New Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill; 2010.
9. Gropper SS, Smith JL. Advanced Nutrition and Human Metabolism. 7th ed. Boston: Cengage Learning; 2018.
10. Webb GP. Nutraceuticals and Functional Foods. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell; 2006.
11. Aluko RE. Functional Foods and Nutraceuticals. New York: Springer; 2012.
12. Harborne JB. Phytochemical Methods. 3rd ed. London: Springer; 1998.
13. Peter KV. Handbook of Herbs and Spices. Cambridge: Woodhead Publishing; 2012.
14. Murray MT. The Encyclopedia of Healing Foods. New York: Atria Books; 2005.
15. Belitz HD, Grosch W, Schieberle P. Food Chemistry. 4th ed. Berlin: Springer; 2009
16. Nadkarni AK. Indian Materia Medica. Mumbai: Popular Prakashan; 2009.
17. Kar A. Pharmacognosy and Pharmacobiotechnology. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers; 2007.
18. Tripathi KD. Essentials of Medical Pharmacology. 8th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers; 2019.
19. deMan JM. Principles of Food Chemistry. 4th ed. Switzerland: Springer; 2018.
20. Weiss RF, Fintelmann V. Herbal Medicine. Stuttgart: Thieme Medical Publishers; 2001.\
21. Ding Y, Lin HW, Lin YL, Yang DJ, Yu YS, Chen JW, et al. Nutritional composition in the chia seed and its processing properties on restructured ham-like products. J Food Drug Anal. 2018;26(1):124-34.
22. Capitani MI, Spotorno V, Nolasco SM, Tomás MC. Physicochemical and functional characterization of by-products from chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.) seeds. LWT Food Sci Technol. 2012;45(1):94-102.
23. Reyes-Caudillo E, Tecante A, Valdivia-López MÁ. Dietary fibre content and antioxidant activity of phenolic compounds present in Mexican chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.) seeds. Food Chem. 2008;107(2):656-63.
24. da Silva BP, Anunciação PC, Matyelka JC, Della Lucia CM, Martino HS, Pinheiro-Sant'Ana HM. Chemical composition of Brazilian chia seeds grown in different places. Food Chem. 2017;221:1709-16.
25. Segura-Campos MR, Salazar-Vega IM, Chel-Guerrero LA, Betancur-Ancona DA. Biological potential of chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.) protein hydrolysates. Food Sci Technol. 2013;33(1):98-103.

HOW TO CITE: Lande Sanika, Vighe Shital, Wable Aniket, Sinare Omkar, Datir Vinay, Jadhav Gayatri, Gaikwad Vijay, Formulation And Preliminary Evaluation of Chia Seeds (*Salvia Hispanica*) Powder as A Functional Health Supplement, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2026, Vol 4, Issue 6, 667-676, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20525768>

